

PEDAGOGY

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING

Alimov Sh.

Professor, Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages, Uzbekistan

Abstract

This article discusses the peculiarities and aims of using interactive methods in teaching foreign languages. The role of interactive methods in activating students and improving their learning outcomes on the basis of psychological and didactic factors are analyzed and highlighted.

Keywords: interactive, activity, effective, learning outcomes, motivation, activate, creative, acquire, improve, skills.

At present, the globalization and integration processes, which is going on throughout of the world, exists a need to gain integrated knowledge related on different spheres of social activity. It has become the reason for working out different methods of activating students in the process of acquiring knowledge, which based on the interpersonal and intrapersonal abilities, interests, desire and motivation of students.

The word "interactive method" is taken from the English word "interactive" which means interpersonal and intrapersonal activity, aimed to activate the learners in gaining knowledge effectively. The main aim of interactive method is to involve all the students in the group to active participation at the lesson. This gives the students opportunity to acquire knowledge with interest and without psychological pressure. In interactive approach, organizing teaching process is based on the following factors:

- the relation of the teacher with students;
 - all round communication;
 - developing the knowledge of students;
 - using feedback after presentation the teaching material;
- (this helps to define comprehension).
- activating students by using different tools and methods;
 - creating self-control;

Interactive methods belong to a group of methods based on the modern psychological conception of interaction. In other words, it is a cooperative activity of the learners during interpersonal communication. The main feature of interaction is realization the ability of a person in acting the role of the other person, to understand a partner in the process of communication, act according to the situations, and construct his / her own activity.

Interactive methods of teaching are worked out according to the project "Reading and writing for critical thinking" (RWCT) which is being implemented into cooperative activity of the teachers from many countries. The main purpose of this project is to implement into education the methods, which serve for improving critical thinking in the learners in spite of their age. In other words they are universal methods of teaching. These methods can easily be used in teaching foreign languages in traditional forms of organizing teaching too. The main idea of interactive methods is to improve critical thinking as constructive intellectual activity,

which suppose intraconscious activity of a person in receiving information. Within the framework of the interactive methods there have been worked out the basis of teaching and learning. It consists of three stages: challenging stage, comprehension stage and reflective stage. At the challenging stage the learners are motivated to learn the theme which is being presented and on the bases of their previous knowledge make diagnosis concerning to the meaning of new information.

At the comprehension stage, the learners work on the text and integrate ideas put in the text based on their own ideas so that they understand the new information better and clearly. At the stage of reflection, the learner's analyses the new information creatively with the purpose of enlarging their knowledge and be able to use it in their further activities.

At present, the following methods as cluster, comparative diagram, puzzle, oriented teaching and others are widely used in teaching foreign languages. Cluster is used for motivating learners to the theme they are learning. In using this method, a teacher writes a word in the center of the blackboard and asks the learners to write around it all the words, which have relations with the key word. After that, they exchange their ideas working in pairs.

The methodology of using interactive methods turn learners into active participants at the lessons, so that they acquire knowledge not passively as in traditional method but actively taking an active part at the discussions. Interactive methods help the foreign language learners to overcome the difficulties, by asking questions because they want to know the reasons of existing difficulties. The active participation of the foreign language learners at the lessons creates favorable conditions for conscious learning, which leads to better understanding the topic.

Interactive methods are not used only for activating learners, but they are the best means of achieving guaranteed results in teaching a foreign language too. Here are we would like to present some positive features of using interactive methods:

1. The learners acquire knowledge with interests and this activates them in the process of learning;
2. The activity of the learners during the lessons create favorable conditions for improving problem-solving skills in them;

3. Require individual approach in teaching i.e. favours for student oriented teaching, which takes into account personal features of the learners;

4. A pair work and group work are emphasized and this will improve the feeling of responsibility in the learners;

5. The skills of independent work are developed in the learners, and the learners using interactive methods acquire knowledge, improve analyzing and creative thinking skills.

6. The interactive methods create strong motivation for learning and involve the learners into active work in implementing the acquired knowledge into practice;

7. Creates a need and high desire to use a foreign language for communication. Moreover, these are good facilities for the learners to express their own ideas and being involved into conversation;

8. A belief for their own strength is formed in the learners and this will help them to overcome such psychological barriers as threat of making mistakes and hesitation;

9. Create favourable opportunities for out of lesson activities, improve the skills of defending their ideas in the process of discourse.

In traditional methods all efforts of the teachers are focused on creating different ways of transforming information and the learners acquire this information passively so that to retell it the next time.

In interactive methods, gaining or acquiring knowledge is the first step and the next steps in this sphere include the activities relating to use this information in practice. This is an active process because the learners actively try to use the gained knowledge in different speech situations. This of course improves their communicative skills. The activity of the learners positively influences on their behavior. The only disadvantage here is noise in the class because the learners actively express their own ideas, feelings with joy and satisfaction. They are not afraid of making mistakes while discussing the problems and exchanging informations.

The module of multilevel communication, which is characteristic for interactive method, creates such an atmosphere in which the learners try to exchange their opinions, express emotions, impressions freely without any hesitation. The module of multilevel communication speech and improves listening skills and sub – skills.

Gamefication is the best tool of activating learners of a foreign language. Using games in organizing teaching process is characteristic not only in teaching young children, but also beneficial in teaching adults. Games

involve both weak and strong students by improving interest and desire, which creates motivation in acquiring knowledge and forming speech skills. Such activities that based on games give satisfaction to the learners, improve collaborative, communicative and problem-solving skills in them. Therefore, teacher's task in using interactive methods is to select appropriate to the educational task exercises and speech situations. The role of speech situations should also be enhanced as they create favourable conditions for activating students. In such conditions, the learners feel themselves free and this will help them to overcome psychological obstacle as fear of making mistakes.

Role-playing is also characteristic for interactive method. It brings joy into teaching process and makes it more interesting. In using this method, a teacher should take into account the individual characteristic features of the students. While acting their roles the students try to express their feelings freely and demonstrate their creative ability. Everybody try to act well. Such high motive in their activities will guarantee the effectivity of teaching and serve as a stimulating tool for further development of the learning outcomes of the students in learning a foreign language.

In conclusion, we would like to stress once more the effectivity of using interactive methods in the educational process in creating motivation in the learners and turning them from passive listeners into active participants. The main goal of using interactive methods is to activate students in the process of acquiring knowledge. Interactive methods involve the students into active participation while acquiring knowledge and improving their speech skills. In this case, they acquire knowledge with interest, desire and high motivation.

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